

Clinical diversity in trials from a Cochrane systematic review of targeted oxygen therapy in the intensive care unit – protocol for a systematic evaluation

Thomas Lass Klitgaard MD PhD,^{1,*} Bodil Steen Rasmussen MD PhD,^{1,2}

Olav Lilleholt Schjørring MD PhD,^{1,2} Frederik Mølgaard Nielsen MD,^{1,2}

Elena Crescioli MD,^{1,2} Jørn Wetterslev MD PhD,³ and Marija Barbateskovic MSc PhD⁴

¹ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

² Department of Clinical Medicine, Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark

³ Private Office, Tuborg Sundpark, 2900 Hellerup, Denmark

⁴ Copenhagen Trial Unit, Centre for Clinical Intervention Research, Rigshospitalet, Copenhagen University Hospital, Copenhagen, Denmark

* Corresponding author. Email: tlk@rn.dk. Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Hobrovej 18-22, 9000 Aalborg, Denmark.

ORCID:

Thomas Lass Klitgaard: [0000-0002-8781-1206](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8781-1206)

Bodil Steen Rasmussen: [0000-0003-2190-145X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2190-145X)

Olav Lilleholt Schjørring: [0000-0002-7749-6003](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7749-6003)

Frederik Mølgaard Nielsen: [0000-0002-0071-1203](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0071-1203)

Elena Crescioli: [0000-0002-8267-7634](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8267-7634)

Jørn Wetterslev: [0000-0001-7778-1771](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7778-1771)

Marija Barbateskovic: [0000-0001-8566-3660](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8566-3660)

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Abstract

Introduction

Oxygen therapy is used extensively in the intensive care unit (ICU) to prevent or treat hypoxaemia. However, the current evidence is insufficient to determine the optimum dosage of supplementary oxygen, and conducted meta-analyses of randomised clinical trials assume comparability across clinical aspects of included trials without accounting for potential clinical diversity.

Objectives

We aim to assess the potential clinical diversity of trials identified in a recent Cochrane review evaluating higher versus lower oxygenation strategies in the ICU and ascertain the implications for the interpretation of the current evidence on this topic.

Methods

We will update the search from the Cochrane review to ensure all recently published trial results have been included. We will systematically search the Cochrane Trial database (CENTRAL), MEDLINE, Embase, Science Citation Index, BIOSIS Previews, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Latin American and Caribbean Health Sciences Literature (LILACS), clinicaltrials.gov, International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP), EU Clinical Trials Register, and the Australian New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry (ANZCTR) for relevant trials. Reference lists of included trial reports, reviews, relevant papers, randomised and non-randomised trials, and editorials will be screened for potential additional relevant trials. Meta-analyses will be performed on the outcomes all-cause mortality, serious adverse events, and quality of life. We will use a novel tool to map and assess the clinical diversity of trials in meta-analyses that scores diversity in four domains: setting, population, intervention, and outcome. A total of 11 items are covered by the tool: years reported, performed in developed vs developing country, and unit type; age; sex; inclusion criteria and baseline severity of illness; comorbidities; diversity of intervention; timing; control intervention; cointerventions; definitions of outcomes; and timing of outcome measurement. We will explore the possible impact of clinical diversity using subgroup meta-analyses and meta-regression analyses where appropriate.

Dissemination

The results of this study will be published regardless of the findings, preferably in a relevant, high-quality, peer-reviewed journal.

Introduction

The provision of oxygen therapy to critically ill patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) is regarded as essential and is used to either treat or prevent low levels of oxygen in the blood (i.e. hypoxaemia). Historically this practice has been characterised by a substantial margin of safety, resulting in a proportion of patients having supra-normal oxygen levels in their blood (i.e. hyperoxaemia).¹⁻³ Several large-scale, randomised clinical trials (RCTs) on oxygen therapy strategies in ICU patients have in recent years been published,⁴⁻⁹ and though all were conducted in the ICU, the trials differ vastly concerning in- and exclusion criteria, applied interventions, and length of follow-up. Some trials have suggested harm of higher oxygenation strategies,^{4,5} or harm of lower oxygenation strategies,⁶ whilst others have suggested equipoise.⁷⁻⁹ Hence, the effects of supplemental oxygen are still a matter of debate, and the optimum dosage for ICU patients remains uncertain. The most recently published Cochrane review suggested a potential decrease in mortality for patients treated with a lower fraction of inspired oxygen (FiO₂) or level of oxygenation as compared with a higher. However, the supporting evidence is of low to very-low certainty.¹⁰ We have recently updated this review and submitted the results in January 2022 (unpublished data).¹¹

Meta-analyses of well-conducted, high-quality, RCTs are regarded as the highest level of evidence and they are used as the basis for constructing clinical guidelines and informing health care decisions.¹² A prerequisite in meta-analyses is that included trials should be clinically homogeneous. However, this may not always be the case. Heterogeneity in RCTs may stem from a variety of reasons such as setting (e.g. type of ICU), population studied (defined by in- and exclusion criteria), applied interventions, duration of interventions, time to follow-up, and measurement or definition of outcomes. Substantial heterogeneity among included RCTs in a meta-analysis may impede interpretations of findings, even when presented with seemingly low outcome-based statistical heterogeneity (e.g. assessed by using Tau² or I²-statistics). This is termed clinical diversity and may be undetected. Traditionally, clinical diversity has been explored using subgroup meta-analyses, but can also be investigated by performing meta-regression analyses.¹³

In this study, we will evaluate all RCTs identified in a recent Cochrane review on higher versus lower FiO₂ or targets of oxygenation in adult patients admitted to the ICU.¹¹ We will update the search from the Cochrane review to ensure that all recently published trial results have been included. Meta-analyses will be performed on the co-primary outcomes as defined in the review: all-cause mortality, serious adverse events (SAEs), and quality of life (QoL). We will systematically, and in detail, describe the potential clinical diversity between identified RCTs using a novel tool specifically designed for this purpose.¹⁴ We will also

evaluate the potential effects of clinical diversity on the interpretation of the overall effect of targeted oxygen therapy in this population.

Overall question: What is the extent of clinical diversity in trials on higher versus lower FiO₂ or targets of oxygenation in adult patients admitted to the ICU, and what implications does this potential diversity have on the interpretation of current evidence?

Methods

Protocol

This protocol was finalised and approved by all authors, and uploaded to zenodo.org, before initiating the outlined study. The study protocol is prepared per the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 statement and supplied in the appendix.¹⁵ We will overall apply the same methodology as in the recent Cochrane review.^{10,16}

Search strategy and data extraction

We will use the same search strategy as used in the most recent Cochrane review on this matter.¹¹ The search strategy is supplied in the appendix. We will search the following databases: Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), MEDLINE, Embase, Science Citation Index, BIOSIS Previews, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), and Latin American and Caribbean Health Science Information database (LILACS). In addition, we will search for ongoing and unpublished trials using the following trial registers: US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register ClinicalTrials.gov (clinicaltrials.gov), World Health Organization (WHO) International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP), EU Clinical Trials Register (www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu), and Australian New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry (ANZCTR) (www.anzctr.org.au). We will for systematic reviews in Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org). Backward and forward citation searches for all included trials will be performed using Web of Science. We will also check for retractions using the Retraction Watch database (retractiondatabase.org). Lastly, we will manually screen the reference lists of included trial reports, reviews, relevant papers, randomised and non-randomised trials, and editorials for potentially relevant trials.

A minimum of two review authors, will independently and in pair, screen each title and abstract of all reports identified by the searches. We will obtain the full texts of those reports deemed potentially relevant and assess these for inclusion in this study. Any disagreements will be resolved by consensus or by consulting a third review author when necessary. We will use the web-based Covidence systematic review software (Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia), available at [covidence.org](https://www.covidence.org) for handling the literature search.

A minimum of two review authors, will independently and in pair, extract relevant data from all reports identified by the searches. Any disagreements will be resolved by consensus or by consulting a third review author when necessary.

Eligibility criteria

We will include RCTs according to the most recent Cochrane Reviews in- and exclusion criteria,¹¹ irrespective of publication status, reported outcomes, publication date, and language. We will include unpublished trials only if methodological descriptions and trial data are provided by direct contact with trial authors or in written form. We will exclude randomised cross-over trials, cluster-randomised trials, and quasi-randomised trials. We will include trials on any adult patients (≥ 18 years) at ICU admission, and only include participants if they are admitted to the ICU before randomisation.

Trials with a clear differentiation in randomisation to either a high or a low oxygen supplementation strategy will be included. We will include both mechanically ventilated and non-mechanically ventilated adult patients. We will exclude RCTs/participants randomised to hypoxaemia (fraction of inspired oxygen [FiO_2] < 0.21 , arterial oxygen saturation [SaO_2] or peripheral oxygen saturation [SpO_2] $< 80\%$, or partial pressure of arterial oxygen [PaO_2] < 6 kPa). Interventions including hyperbaric oxygen will be excluded.

Description of trials

We will describe the following characteristics for the identified trials: year of publication; setting; baseline severity of illness score; median/mean age of included patients; percentage of men; in- and exclusion criteria; treatments used in the intervention and in the control groups, including duration and timing of these; and outcomes.

Definition of treatment groups

We define the group receiving the higher level of FiO_2 or oxygenation target (PaO_2 , SaO_2 , SpO_2 , or a combination of such) as the experimental intervention, and the group receiving the lower level of FiO_2 or oxygenation target (PaO_2 , SaO_2 , SpO_2 , or combination of such) as the control intervention.

Outcomes

For this study, we will focus on the co-primary outcomes of the Cochrane review (all-cause mortality, proportion of participants with one or more SAEs, and QoL) and use the same definitions of such as in the review.¹⁶ We will also consider the highest reported proportion of SAEs and cumulated number of SAEs, and individual SAEs. We may choose to explore what this outcome encompasses in the included trials in case we find high diversity or lack of diversity. We will only consider outcomes at longest follow-up as

reported in the identified trials. Two authors will independently extract data on outcomes. Any disagreement will be resolved by discussion or by consulting a third author.

Assessment of clinical diversity

We will use the novel tool for assessment of Clinical Diversity In Meta-analyses (CDIM) to evaluate the clinical diversity between the included trials in the meta-analysis of all-cause mortality, SAEs, and QoL life.¹⁴ The CDIM tool has been developed and validated specifically to assess clinical diversity between clinical trials in meta-analyses for multiple purposes: 1) to be used as a mapping and screening tool that may point out clinical characteristics that ought to be explored further; 2) the scoring will enable authors *post-hoc* and in future updates of their review to explore factors that might modify intervention effects notably, and in that way identify potential effect modifiers; and 3) systematic reviewers may easily incorporate a plan in their protocol for a new systematic review to use CDIM to check whether possible clinical diversity has been explored sufficiently. CDIM can then be used to define and select subgroup analyses as items with a score of 2 are suggested to be explored in subgroup analyses. Consequently, CDIM can be used prospectively to select sub-group analyses.

The CDIM tool measures clinical diversity on an ordinal scale in four domains with eleven items in total. Each item is assigned a score of 0 (i.e. no difference), 1 (i.e. slight variation), or 2 (i.e. considerable variation), and the combined score (CDIMS) thus ranges from 0 to 22, i.e. from 'no clinical diversity detected' to 'abundant clinical diversity in all CDIM domains'. Below is a list of the explored domains and items.

Domain 1: Setting diversity

- Time of conduct (or year of publication if time is not available), type of country development status (i.e. developing or non-developing), and localization within the health care system (i.e. ICU, general ward, etc.)

Domain 2: Population diversity

- Age
- Sex
- Inclusion criteria and baseline disease severity
- Comorbidities

Domain 3: Intervention diversity

- Diversity of intervention (e.g. dose, duration of intervention, etc.)
- Timing of intervention(s)
- Diversity of control-interventions
- Use of cointerventions

Domain 4: Outcomes

- Definition of outcome
- Timing of outcome assessment(s)

Each trial included in the meta-analysis will be evaluated using the CDIM tool by at least two independent assessors. Any disagreement will be resolved by discussion or by consulting a third author.

Items having 2 CDIM points will be further investigated by subgroup analyses and meta-regression in terms of the association with treatment effect as proposed by the clinical diversity described in the relevant item.

Risk of bias

Risk of bias will be assessed using the 'Risk of Bias 2' (RoB-2) tool.^{17,18} Two authors will independently and in pair assess the risk of bias. Any disagreements will be resolved by consensus or by consulting a third review author when necessary.

Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses will be conducted using STATA statistical software (StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX, USA). For dichotomous outcomes, we will calculate the relative risk (RR), and the absolute difference for continuous outcomes. We will present estimates with 95% confidence intervals (CI), considering an alpha-level of 0.05 as statistically significant, thus no adjustment for multiplicity will be conducted. Statistical between-study heterogeneity will be assessed using the Chi² test, with $p \leq 0.10$ indicating significance. We will also assess heterogeneity by means of the I² statistic.¹⁹ We will regard an I² statistic of $\leq 30\%$ as 'low', $>30\%$ to $\leq 60\%$ as 'moderate', and $>60\%$ as 'high'.¹⁴ Heterogeneity will be visually assessed using forest plots.

Meta-analyses

We will conduct meta-analyses of all-cause mortality, SAEs, and QoL at longest follow-up using both random-effects (DerSimonian-Laird)²⁰ and fixed-effect (Mantel-Haenszel)²¹ models as according to the

specified review.¹⁶ We will report the most extreme outcome (i.e. indicating most harm), being the point estimate furthest from the null-effect (i.e. RR = 1, and absolute difference = 0) as the primary result. Results from both models will be reported.

We will perform subgroup analyses of identified outcomes based on risk of bias assessed by the Cochrane RoB-2 tool,^{17,18} and also if equivalent subgroup analyses have not been performed in relevant reviews of this matter as informed by the CDIM tool to represent 'considerable variation' (i.e. 2 CDIM points).

Subgroup analyses performed in the Cochrane review:

1. According to overall risk of bias:
 - a. overall low risk of bias
 - b. overall some concern
 - c. overall high risk of bias
2. According to different types of oxygen interventions:
 - a. oxygenation target measured using either PaO₂ or SaO₂ or SpO₂ (as defined by trialists)
 - b. oxygen level defined by FiO₂ (as defined and set by trialists)
 - c. difference between groups (as defined by trialists)
3. According to FiO₂ or oxygenation/target in the higher-oxygen administration group:
 - a. low targets defined as FiO₂ of 0.5 or lower or PaO₂ of 10 kPa or lower or SaO₂/SpO₂ of 95% or lower
 - b. high targets defined as FiO₂ above 0.5 or PaO₂ above 10 kPa or SaO₂/SpO₂ above 95%
4. According to FiO₂ or oxygenation/target in the lower-oxygen administration group:
 - a. low targets defined as FiO₂ between or at 0.21 to 0.30 or PaO₂ between or at 6 kPa to 8 kPa or SaO₂/SpO₂ between or at 85% to 90%
 - b. high targets defined as FiO₂ above 0.30 to 0.40 or PaO₂ above 8 kPa to 10 kPa or SaO₂/SpO₂ above 90%
5. According to ICU population:
 - a. medical
 - b. surgical
 - c. mixed
 - d. adults with any respiratory failure
 - e. adults with any cerebral disease
 - f. adults with any heart disease
 - g. adults with any trauma

- h. adults with COPD
6. According to oxygen delivery system:
- a. invasive mechanical ventilation with an endotracheal tube
 - b. any non-invasive oxygen administration
 - c. mixed oxygen delivery system

Meta-regression analyses

Domains identified by the CDIM tool to represent 'considerable variation' (i.e. 2 CDIM points) will be included in meta-regression analyses (univariate and multivariate) of mortality, SAEs, and QoL to evaluate the possible effect modification of such domains. Continuous co-variables (e.g. median/mean age of included patients; percentage of women; duration of intervention; timing of outcome measurement) and categorical covariates (e.g. outcome definition) will be treated as continuous or categorical variables, respectively. Meta-regression analyses will be performed using a random-effects model to incorporate residual intervention heterogeneity not explained by the investigated parameters.¹³

Missing data

To assess the impact of missing data we will perform best-worst and worst-best case scenarios as according to the Cochrane review.^{10,11,16}

Reporting bias

Reporting bias will be assessed using funnel plots if ten or more trials report on an outcome. Asymmetry will be tested using the Harbord test for dichotomous outcomes,²² and for continuous outcomes the Egger test.²³

Quality of evidence

We will assess the certainty of evidence for all prespecified outcomes according to the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE) system.^{24,25} We will present the results of the GRADE assessment in the 'Summary of findings' table.

Discussion

Conduct of meta-analyses requires a reasonable degree of comparability among trials included with regards to e.g. setting, patient population, interventions, and outcomes utilised. Clinical interpretation of findings may be impeded if trials identified in systematic reviews, and compared in meta-analyses, are highly diverse. By using the novel CDIM tool we aim to systematically evaluate the clinical diversity of trials included in a meta-analysis investigating the effects of higher versus lower FiO_2 or oxygenation levels in adult ICU patients, and to further incorporate this information in updated meta-analyses, subgroup analyses, and meta-regression analyses. However, as the findings of this study will only be able to investigate confounding factors on a trial-based level, important patients-based factors may therefore still not be accounted for and potentially influence the overall effect estimate. Nevertheless, the use of the CDIM tool will potentially identify important areas of probable confounders that are relevant to account for in future trials and investigations on this subject.

Dissemination and publication

All results will be published regardless of findings, preferably in a relevant high-quality, peer-reviewed journal.

Schedule

Medio 2022:	Writing study protocol.
Ultimo 2022:	Literature search, screening, CDIM assessment and compiling results.
Primo-Ultimo 2023:	Writing primary draft.
Primo 2024:	Submission of paper to peer-reviewed journal.

Participants

The study group consists of:

Thomas Lass Klitgaard, MD PhD: Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

Bodil Steen Rasmussen, MD PhD: Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

Olav Lilleholt Schjørring, MD PhD: Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

Frederik Mølgaard Nielsen, MD: Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

Elena Crescioli, MD: Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Aalborg University Hospital, Aalborg, Denmark

Jørn Wetterslev, MD PhD: Private Office, Tuborg Sundpark, 2900 Hellerup, Denmark

Marija Barbateskovic, MSc PhD: Copenhagen Trial Unit, Copenhagen University Hospital, Copenhagen, Denmark

Author contributions

TLK wrote the first draft. All authors critically revised the protocol and approved the final version.

Conflicts of interest

- MB and JW partook in developing the CDIM tool.
- TLK, OLS, JW, and BSR are involved in the conduct of the 'Handling Oxygenation Targets in the Intensive Care Unit' (HOT-ICU) trial investigating a lower versus a higher oxygenation target in adult ICU patients with hypoxaemic respiratory failure.
- TLK, FMN, OLS, JW, and BSR are involved in the conduct of the 'Handling Oxygenation Targets in COVID-19' (HOT-COVID) trial investigating a lower versus a higher oxygenation target in adult ICU patients with COVID-19.
- TLK, BSR, OLS, FMN, JW, and MB are involved in updating the Cochrane review: Klitgaard, TL et al., *Higher or lower fractions of inspired oxygen or targets of arterial oxygenation for adults admitted to the intensive care unit*. Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews, Art. No.: CD012631. DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD012631.pub2.
- BSR, OLS, JW, and MB co-authored a systematic review on oxygen targets in acutely ill adults: Barbateskovic M et al., *Higher vs Lower Oxygenation Strategies in Acutely Ill Adults*. Chest; 2020; 159: 154–73. DOI: 10.1016/j.chest.2020.07.015

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PRISMA 2020 Checklist

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Page 1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Page 3
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Pages 4-5
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Page 5
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Page 7
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Page 6
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Pages 23-33
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Pages 6-7
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 6
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Pages 7-8
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Page 6
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 9
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Page 9-10
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Page 7
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Pages 9-11

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Pages 9 + 11
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Pages 9-11
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Pages 10-11
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Pages 10-11
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Page 11
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Page 11
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	N/A
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	N/A
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	N/A
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	N/A
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	N/A
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	N/A
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	N/A
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	N/A
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	N/A
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	N/A
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	N/A

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Page 12
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	N/A
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	N/A
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	N/A
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	Page 6
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Page 6
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	N/A
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Page 14
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Pages 13-14
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	N/A

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

The Clinical Diversity In Meta-analyses (CDIM) tool

Domains of diversity	Items	Score	Explanation of score for extreme differences between trials in a meta-analysis
Setting	1. A) Year reported B) Performed in developed vs developing country C) Type of unit	0	No differences: A) years reported differ < 15 and B) No developed vs developing countries and C) slight variations in the unit or facility type and there is low risk of affecting other fields of diversity
		1	Slight variation (at least one of A-C involved): A) years reported differ ≥ 15 or B) developed vs developing countries or treating units not similar or C) if there are slight variations in the unit or facility type but there is risk of affecting other fields of diversity
		2	Considerable variation (all of A-C involved): A) years reported differ ≥ 15 and B) developed vs developing countries and C) treating units not similar (all of A-C involved) or if the trials in the opinion of the assessor differs markedly in setting diversity
Population	2. Age	0	Mean/median age ≤10 years difference
		1	11–20 years difference in mean/median age
		2	Mean/median age >20 years difference
	3. Sex	0	Percentage of women ≤20% absolute difference between trials
		1	21%–30% absolute difference of percentage of women between trials
		2	>30% absolute difference of women between trials
4. Inclusion criteria and baseline disease severity	0	Patients are equally ill among trials or the difference in risk/score for disease severity of patients ≤20%	
	1	Patient populations differs slightly with ≥50% overlap of types of participants and/or the difference in risk/score for disease severity of patients is 21%–30%	
	2	Patient population differs considerable and/or the difference in risk/score for disease severity of patients >30%	
5. Comorbidities	0	Difference in frequency of important comorbidities ≤20% or no comorbidities are reported in the included trials and differences in comorbidities are assumed absent	
	1	Slight differences in important comorbidities, between 21% and 30%, or no comorbidities are reported in the trials, but differences in comorbidities are assumed	
	2	Differences in frequency of important comorbidities >30% OR highly likely variations in comorbidities	
Intervention	6. Intensity, strengths, or duration of intervention	0	Little variation: differences in dose, strengths, devices, cut-offs, OR duration of interventions ≤20%
		1	Slight variation: 21% to 30% differences in dose, strengths, devices, cut-offs, or duration

			intervention, or if dose, strength, cut-offs or duration of intervention cannot be assessed from the information in the included trials
		2	Considerable variation if different types of interventions are used, or different doses, strengths, devices, cut-offs, or duration of intervention >30%
	7. Timing	0	Criteria for starting the intervention are similar, or relative differences of timing of intervention differ ≤20%
		1	Criteria for starting the intervention differ slightly, or the relative timing difference is 21%-30%
		2	Criteria for starting the intervention differ, or relative timing difference exceeds >30%
	8. Control intervention	0	All control interventions are the same
		1	Control interventions include placebo and no intervention (assess as item 6 if an active intervention is used)
		2	Including trials with different active control interventions or trials with active and placebo/no intervention
	9. Cointerventions	0	No apparent differences in cointerventions or standard care is not described or assumed to be the same, or equally applied in groups, or different cointerventions are used, but the effects of the cointerventions are assumed to be small
		1	Slight variation in cointerventions, or the same cointerventions are used with slight variation (< 30% difference in, e.g., doses or numbers of participants using the cointervention)
		2	Considerable differences if it is assumed that the cointervention is not usual care, or differences in use OR, e.g., doses of cointerventions > 30%
Outcome	10. Definition of the outcome in the meta-analysis	0	Same definition of outcome
		1	Slight variations in definition of outcome
		2	Considerable variations in definition of outcome
	11. Timing of outcome measurement	0	Less than one month between follow-up of outcome
		1	More than one but less than or equal to 3 months between follow-ups
		2	More than 3 months between follow-up of outcome

Adapted from Barbateskovic et. al 2021.¹⁴

Literature search

Ovid MEDLINE

- 1 exp Hyperoxia/
- 2 exp Anoxia/
- 3 exp Oxygen Inhalation Therapy/
- 4 exp Oxygen/
- 5 ((inspir* or inhal* or fraction* or concentrat* or arterial* or saturation or level* or tension* or supply* or supplement* or supplie* or therap* or administr* or dosag* or dose* or dosing*) adj3 oxygen).tw.
- 6 (hyperoxia or hyperoxemia or hyperoxaemia or hypoxia or hypoxemia or hypoxaemia or anoxia or anoxemia or anoxaemia or arterial oxygen or high oxygen or oxygenat* or blood gas or oxygen saturation or pao2 or sao2 or spo2 or fio2).tw.
- 7 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6
- 8 exp Critical Illness/
- 9 exp Critical Care/
- 10 exp Intensive Care Units/
- 11 exp Emergency Medicine/
- 12 exp Emergency Service, Hospital/
- 13 (emergency department* or ED or emergency room* or ER or high dependency unit* or HDU or prehospital* or pre-hospital* or critical illness or critically ill or acutely ill or intensive care or critical care or ICU* or coronary care unit* or neurological intermediate care unit*).tw.
- 14 exp Heart Arrest/
- 15 exp Myocardial Ischemia/
- 16 (cardiac arrest or cardiac failure or CPR or heart arrest or heart failure or myocardial infarct* or myocardial ischemia or acute coronary syndrome).tw. (434515)
- 17 exp Shock/
- 18 shock.tw.
- 19 exp Meningitis/
- 20 meningitis.tw.
- 21 exp Pneumonia/
- 22 pneumonia.tw.
- 23 exp Pulmonary Disease, Chronic Obstructive/
- 24 (COPD or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease).tw.
- 25 exp Acute Lung Injury/
- 26 (acute lung injury or ALI).tw.
- 27 exp Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Adult/
- 28 (((adult or acute) adj2 respiratory distress) or ARDS).tw.
- 29 exp Pulmonary Embolism/
- 30 ((pulmonary or lung) adj (embolism or infarct*)).tw.
- 31 exp Multiple Trauma/
- 32 (severe trauma or multiple trauma).tw.
- 33 exp Craniocerebral Trauma/
- 34 (traumatic brain injury or TBI or head trauma or craniocerebral trauma).tw.
- 35 exp Stroke/

36 stroke.tw.
37 exp Sepsis/
38 exp Shock, Septic/
39 (sepsis or septic shock).tw.
40 exp Intracranial Hemorrhages/
41 ((intracranial or intra-cranial or subarachnoid or cerebral or life-threatening) adj2 (hemorrhage or haemorrhage or bleeding)).tw.
42 exp Poisoning/
43 (severe adj (poisoning or intoxication*)).tw.
44 exp Diabetic Ketoacidosis/
45 diabetic ketoacidosis.tw.
46 exp Liver Failure, Acute/
47 (acute hepatic failure* or fulminating hepatic failure* or acute liver failure*).tw.
48 exp Acute Kidney Injury/
49 (acute kidney failure* or acute renal injur*).tw.
50 exp Intestinal Perforation/
51 exp Appendicitis/
52 (intestinal perforation* or appendicitis).tw.
53 ((acute or emergency) adj2 (surgery or surgical or operat* or resection*)).tw.
54 exp Coronavirus/
55 exp Coronavirus Infections/
56 exp COVID-19/
57 (coronavirus or corona virus or covid or covid2019 or covid19 or SARS2 or SARS-CoV-2 or SARS-CoV-19 or severe acute respiratory pneumonia outbreak or novel cov or 2019ncov or sars cov2 or cov22 or ncov or coronaviridae).tw.
58 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54 or 55 or 56 or 57
59 7 and 58
60 randomised controlled trial.pt.
61 controlled clinical trial.pt.
62 randomi?ed.ab.
63 placebo.ab.
64 clinical trial.sh.
65 randomly.ab.
66 trial.ti.
67 60 or 61 or 62 or 63 or 64 or 65 or 66
68 exp animals/ not humans.sh.
69 67 not 68
70 59 and 69

Embase

- 1 *hyperoxia/
- 2 *hypoxia/
- 3 *oxygen therapy/
- 4 *oxygen/
- 5 *arterial oxygen saturation/
- 6 *oxygen blood level/
- 7 *arterial oxygen tension/
- 8 *blood oxygen tension/
- 9 ((inspir* or inhal* or fraction* or concentrat* or arterial* or saturation or level* or tension* or supply* or supplement* or supplie* or therap* or administr* or dosag* or dose* or dosing*) adj3 oxygen).tw.
- 10 (hyperoxia or hyperoxemia or hyperoxaemia or hypoxia or hypoxemia or hypoxaemia or anoxia or anoxemia or anoxaemia or arterial oxygen or high oxygen or oxygenat* or blood gas or oxygen saturation or pao2 or sao2 or spo2 or fio2).tw.
- 11 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10
- 12 *critical illness/
- 13 *intensive care/
- 14 *intensive care unit/
- 15 *emergency medicine/
- 16 *emergency health service/
- 17 *coronary care unit/
- 18 (emergency department* or ED or emergency room* or ER or high dependency unit* or HDU or prehospital* or pre-hospital* or critical illness or critically ill or acutely ill or intensive care or critical care or ICU* or coronary care unit* or neurological intermediate care unit*).tw.
- 19 *heart arrest/
- 20 *acute heart infarction/
- 21 (cardiac arrest or cardiac failure* or CPR or heart arrest or heart failure* or myocardial infarct* or myocardial ischemia or acute coronary syndrome).tw.
- 22 *shock/
- 23 shock.tw.
- 24 *meningitis/
- 25 meningitis.tw.
- 26 *pneumonia/
- 27 pneumonia.tw.
- 28 *chronic obstructive lung disease/
- 29 *acute lung injury/
- 30 (acute lung injur* or ALI).tw.
- 31 (COPD or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease).tw.
- 32 *adult respiratory distress syndrome/
- 33 (((adult or acute) adj2 respiratory distress) or ARDS).tw.
- 34 *lung embolism/
- 35 ((pulmonary or lung) adj (embolism or infarct*)).tw.
- 36 *multiple trauma/
- 37 (severe trauma or multiple trauma).tw.

38 *head injury/
 39 *brain injury/
 40 (traumatic brain injur* or TBI or head trauma or craniocerebral trauma).tw.
 41 *cerebrovascular accident/
 42 *stroke unit/
 43 stroke.tw.
 44 *sepsis/
 45 *septic shock/
 46 (sepsis or septic shock).tw.
 47 *brain hemorrhage/
 48 ((intracranial or intra-cranial or subarachnoid or cerebral or life-threatening) adj2 (hemorrhage or haemorrhage or bleeding)).tw.
 49 *intoxication/
 50 (severe adj (poisoning or intoxication*)).tw.
 51 *diabetic ketoacidosis/
 52 diabetic ketoacidosis.tw.
 53 *acute liver failure/
 54 (acute hepatic failure* or fulminating hepatic failure* or acute liver failure*).tw.
 55 *acute kidney failure/
 56 (acute kidney failure* or acute renal injur*).tw.
 57 *intestine perforation/
 58 *appendicitis/
 59 (intestinal perforation* or appendicitis).tw.
 60 ((acute or emergency) adj2 (surgery or surgical or operat* or resection)).tw.
 61 *coronavirinae/
 62 *coronaviridae infection/
 63 *coronavirus disease 2019/
 64 (coronavirus or corona virus or covid or covid2019 or covid19 or SARS2 or SARS-CoV-2 or SARS-CoV-19 or severe acute respiratory pneumonia outbreak or novel cov or 2019ncov or sars cov2 or cov22 or ncov or coronaviridae).tw.
 65 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53 or 54 or 55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60 or 61 or 62 or 63 or 64
 66 11 and 65
 67 CROSSOVER PROCEDURE.sh.
 68 DOUBLE-BLIND PROCEDURE.sh.
 69 SINGLE-BLIND PROCEDURE.sh.
 70 (crossover* or cross over*).ti,ab.
 71 placebo*.ti,ab.
 72 ((single or double or triple or treble) adj (blind* or mask*)).ti,ab.
 73 allocat*.ti,ab.
 74 trial.ti.
 75 RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIAL.sh.
 76 random*.ti,ab.
 77 67 or 68 or 69 or 70 or 71 or 72 or 73 or 74 or 75 or 76

78 (exp animal/ or exp invertebrate/ or animal.hw. or nonhuman/) not (exp human/ or human cell/ or (human or humans or man or men or wom?n).ti.)

79 77 not 78

80 66 and 79

Central

- #1 MeSH descriptor: [Hyperoxia] explode all trees
- #2 MeSH descriptor: [Hypoxia] explode all trees
- #3 MeSH descriptor: [Oxygen Inhalation Therapy] explode all trees
- #4 MeSH descriptor: [Oxygen] explode all trees
- #5 ((inspir* or inhal* or fraction* or concentrat* or arterial* or saturation or level* or tension* or supply* or supplement* or supplie* or therap* or administr* or dosag* or dose* or dosing*) near/3 oxygen):ti,ab,kw
- #6 (hyperoxia or hyperoxemia or hyperoxaemia or hypoxia or hypoxemia or hypoxaemia or anoxia or anoxemia or anoxaemia or "arterial oxygen" or "high oxygen" or oxygenat* or "blood gas" or "oxygen saturation" or pao2 or sao2 or spo2 or fio2):ti,ab,kw
- #7 (#1 or #2 or #3 or #4 or #5 or #6)
- #8 MeSH descriptor: [Critical Illness] explode all trees
- #9 MeSH descriptor: [Critical Care] explode all trees
- #10 MeSH descriptor: [Intensive Care Units] explode all trees
- #11 MeSH descriptor: [Emergency Medicine] explode all trees
- #12 MeSH descriptor: [Emergency Service, Hospital] explode all trees
- #13 ((emergency next department*) or ED or (emergency next room*) or ER or (high next dependency next unit*) or HDU or prehospital* or pre-hospital* or "critically ill" or "acutely ill" or "intensive care" or "critical care" or ICU* or (coronary next care next unit*) or (neurological next intermediate next care next unit*)):ti,ab,kw
- #14 MeSH descriptor: [Heart Arrest] explode all trees
- #15 MeSH descriptor: [Myocardial Ischemia] explode all trees
- #16 ("cardiac arrest" or (cardiac next failure*) or CPR or "heart arrest" or (heart next failure*) or (myocardial next infarct*) or "myocardial ischemia" or "acute coronary syndrome"):ti,ab,kw 69458
- #17 MeSH descriptor: [Shock] explode all trees
- #18 (shock):ti,ab,kw
- #19 MeSH descriptor: [Meningitis] explode all trees
- #20 (meningitis):ti,ab,kw
- #21 MeSH descriptor: [Pneumonia] explode all trees
- #22 (pneumonia):ti,ab,kw
- #23 MeSH descriptor: [Pulmonary Disease, Chronic Obstructive] explode all trees
- #24 (COPD or "chronic obstructive pulmonary disease"):ti,ab,kw
- #25 MeSH descriptor: [Acute Lung Injury] explode all trees
- #26 ((acute next lung next injur*) or ALI):ti,ab,kw
- #27 MeSH descriptor: [Respiratory Distress Syndrome] explode all trees
- #28 ((adult or acute) near/2 (Respiratory Distress)):ti,ab,kw
- #29 MeSH descriptor: [Pulmonary Embolism] explode all trees
- #30 ((pulmonary or lung) near/2 (embolism or infarct*)):ti,ab,kw
- #31 MeSH descriptor: [Multiple Trauma] explode all trees
- #32 ("severe trauma" or "multiple trauma"):ti,ab,kw
- #33 MeSH descriptor: [Cranio-cerebral Trauma] explode all trees
- #34 ((traumatic next brain next injur*) or TBI or "head trauma" or "cranio-cerebral trauma"):ti,ab,kw
- #35 MeSH descriptor: [Stroke] explode all trees
- #36 (stroke):ti,ab,kw
- #37 MeSH descriptor: [Sepsis] explode all trees
- #38 MeSH descriptor: [Shock, Septic] explode all trees

- #39 (sepsis or "septic shock"):ti,ab,kw
- #40 MeSH descriptor: [Intracranial Hemorrhages] explode all trees
- #41 ((intracranial or intra-cranial or subarachnoid or cerebral or life-threatening) near/2 (hemorrhage or haemorrhage or bleeding)):ti,ab,kw
- #42 MeSH descriptor: [Poisoning] explode all trees
- #43 (severe near/2 (poisoning or intoxication*)):ti,ab,kw
- #44 MeSH descriptor: [Diabetic Ketoacidosis] explode all trees
- #45 ("diabetic ketoacidosis"):ti,ab,kw
- #46 MeSH descriptor: [Liver Failure, Acute] explode all trees
- #47 ((acute next hepatic next failur*) or (fulminating next hepatic next failur*) or (acute next liver next failure*)):ti,ab,kw
- #48 MeSH descriptor: [Acute Kidney Injury] explode all trees
- #49 ((acute next kidney next failur*) or (acute next renal next injur*)):ti,ab,kw
- #50 MeSH descriptor: [Intestinal Perforation] explode all trees
- #51 MeSH descriptor: [Appendicitis] explode all trees
- #52 ((intestinal next perforation*) or appendicitis):ti,ab,kw
- #53 ((acute or emergency) near/2 (surgery or surgical or operat* or resection*)):ti,ab,kw
- #54 MeSH descriptor: [Coronavirus] explode all trees
- #55 MeSH descriptor: [Coronavirus Infections] explode all trees
- #56 MeSH descriptor: [COVID-19] explode all trees
- #57 (coronavirus or "corona virus" or covid or covid2019 or covid19 or SARS2 or SARS-CoV-2 or SARS-CoV-19 or "severe acute respiratory pneumonia outbreak" or "novel cov" or 2019ncov or "sars cov2" or cov22 or ncov or coronaviridae):ti,ab,kw
- #58 (#8 or #9 or #10 or #11 or #12 or #13 or #14 or #15 or #16 or #17 or #18 or #19 or #20 or #21 or #22 or #23 or #24 or #25 or #26 or #27 or #28 or #29 or #30 or #31 or #32 or #33 or #34 or #35 or #36 or #37 or #38 or #39 or #40 or #41 or #42 or #43 or #44 or #45 or #46 or #47 or #48 or #49 or #50 or #51 or #52 or #53 or #54 or #55 or #56 or #57)
- #59 (#7 and #58)
- #60 #59 in Trials

Databases= WOS, BIOSIS Timespan=All years Search language=Auto

5 #4 AND #3

4 TS=((control* OR clinical OR comparative) NEAR/3 (trial* or stud*)) OR TS=random* OR TS=((single or double or triple or treble) NEAR/6 (mask* or blind*)) OR TS=(crossover OR cross-over) OR TS=(factorial* OR placebo* OR volunteer*) OR TI=(trial* or groups)

3 #2 AND #1

2 TS=("emergency department*" or ED or "emergency room*" or ER or "high dependency unit*" or HDU or prehospital* or pre-hospital* or "critical illness" or "critically ill" or "acutely ill" or "intensive care" or "critical care" or ICU* or "coronary care unit*" or "neurological intermediate care unit*") or TS=("cardiac arrest" or "cardiac failure*" or CPR or "heart arrest" or "heart failure*" or "myocardial infarct*" or "myocardial ischemia" or "acute coronary syndrome") or TS=(shock or meningitis or pneumonia or COPD or "chronic obstructive pulmonary disease" or "acute lung injur*" or ALI) or TS=((adult or acute) near/2 (Respiratory Distress)) or TS=(((pulmonary or lung) near/2 (embolism or infarct*)) or "severe trauma" or "multiple trauma" or "traumatic brain injur*" or TBI or "head trauma" or "craniocerebral trauma") or TS=(stroke or sepsis or "septic shock") or TS=((intracranial or intra-cranial or subarachnoid or cerebral or life-threatening) near/2 (hemorrhage or haemorrhage or bleeding)) or TS=("severe poisoning" or "severe intoxication" or "diabetic ketoacidosis" or "acute hepatic failur*" or "fulminating hepatic failur*" or "acute liver failur*") or TS=("acute kidney failur*" or "acute renal injur*" or "intestinal perforation*" or appendicitis or ((acute or emergency) near/2 (surgery or surgical or operat* or resection*))) or TS=(coronavirus or "corona virus" or covid or covid2019 or covid19 or SARS2 or SARS-CoV-2 or SARS-CoV-19 or "severe acute respiratory pneumonia outbreak" or "novel cov" or 2019ncov or "sars cov2" or cov22 or ncov or coronaviridae)

1 TI=((inspir* or inhal* or fraction* or concentrat* or arterial* or saturation or level* or tension* or supply* or supplement* or supplie* or therap* or administr* or dosag* or dose* or dosing*) near/3 oxygen) or TI=(hyperoxia or hyperoxemia or hyperoxaemia or hypoxia or hypoxemia or hypoxaemia or anoxia or anoxemia or anoxaemia or "arterial oxygen" or "high oxygen" or oxygenat* or "blood gas" or "oxygen saturation" or pao2 or sao2 or spo2 or fio2)

LILACS

(hyperoxia or hyperoxemia or hyperoxaemia or hypoxia or hypoxemia or hypoxaemia or anoxia or anoxemia or anoxaemia or oxygen or blood gas or pao2 or sao2 or spo2 or fio2) [Words] and (acute surgery or acute operation or acute resection or emergency surgery or emergency operation or emergency resection) or (intestinal perforation or appendicitis) or (acute kidney failure or acute renal injuries) or (acute hepatic failure or fulminating hepatic failure) or (diabetic ketoacidosis) or (severe poisoning) or (intracranial hemorrhage or subarachnoid hemorrhage or cerebral hemorrhage or intracranial bleeding or life-threatening bleeding) or (sepsis or septic shock) or (stroke) or (traumatic brain injury or TBI or head trauma or craniocerebral trauma) or (severe trauma or multiple trauma) or (pulmonary embolism or pulmonary infarction) or (adult respiratory distress syndrome or ARDS) or (acute lung injury) or (COPD or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease) or (pneumonia) or (meningitis) or (shock) or (cardiac arrest or cardiac failure or CPR or heart arrest or heart failure or myocardial infarction or myocardial ischemia or acute coronary syndrome) or (emergency department or ED or emergency room or ER or high dependency unit or HDU or prehospital or critically ill or acutely ill or intensive care or critical care or ICU or coronary care unit or neurological intermediate care unit or coronavirus or corona virus or covid or SARS2 or SARS-CoV-2 or SARS-CoV-19 or severe acute respiratory pneumonia outbreak or novel cov or 2019ncov or sars cov2 or cov22 or ncov or covid19 or corona viridae) [Words] and (randomised or randomised or random or randomly OR control or controlled OR RCT OR placebo OR group OR trial) [Words]

Trial registries

We will search the following trial registries:

We searched the following trial registries:

- US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register ClinicalTrials.gov (www.clinicaltrials.gov)
- World Health Organization (WHO) International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP) (www.who.int/ictcp/en/)
- EU Clinical Trials Register (www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/)
- Australian New Zealand Clinical Trials Registry (ANZCTR) (www.anzctr.org.au/)

Search combination: "Oxygen" and "Intensive Care", and apply the 'advanced search option' where possible.

Epistemonikos

Strategy:

(title:(title:(oxygen) OR abstract:(oxygen))) OR abstract:(title:(oxygen) OR abstract:(oxygen))) AND
(title:(intensive care unit) OR abstract:(intensive care unit))